

The Aesthetic Design of the Ornaments on the Walls and Door of Al-Mustansiriya School, Baghdad

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Abstract

With the development of humankind and the need for an environment that imposes upon it a certain order and type, the necessity arose to contemplate what could grant Islamic buildings or schools, in earlier times, both aesthetic and functional value within the social reality. Beyond their aesthetic dimensions in terms of design aspects, architecture being one of the earliest forms of art served as a refuge of values in artistic formation, rooted in the nature of the local environment and extending to what became known of architectural arts. These reflected a type of formation in which the architect combined functional and aesthetic aspects in a form of architecture that employed the walls of the gate of the Al-Mustansiriya School, considered both a school and a mosque.

The study sheds light on the reasons for its recognition and use in architecture, as well as the causes behind the formation of the decorations on both sides of the gate, including what is known as the *dankha* or the supporting column of the school's gate. The aim of the research is to identify the structural foundations upon which these walls of the school were built, considering them as complementary to the construction both artistically and functionally. The research emphasizes the importance of addressing this subject as an aspect of creative expression recognized by the Iraqi architect, and as a topic of study for its dual qualities of utility and ornamentation within the building.

Keywords: *decorative art, Muslim artist, design elements, aesthetic value.*

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Introduction

If we wish to trace the growth and development of decorative art, this leads us to identify the various civilizations that came under the expansion of the Islamic state. We can see the influence of a civilization that emerged around the Mediterranean in forming that artistic identity. This abstract tendency in art and architecture also appeared in Central Asia. Architecture became a fertile source for the Muslim artist, the architect, and the designer of ornamentation, with its vocabulary enriched by numerous architectural complements. Vegetal and geometric decorations became part of the world of architectural art, adorning the façades of traditional and Islamic buildings. The Al-Mustansiriya School and Mosque is considered one of the buildings that embodied the principles and elements of design on its walls, through design forms and vegetal and geometric ornaments. These had a great impact on attracting the viewer to observe and appreciate their aesthetic beauty, reflecting the creativity of the Muslim designer in executing and embodying the ornaments, which were inspired by nature and ultimately return to God's creation and to the infinite and eternal realm of both religious and worldly life. They were employed on the façades and walls of the Al-Mustansiriya School and Mosque, as well as on its entrance gate, and materialized in various ways through deep carving, relief, or abstraction. These decorative elements, manifested in all the

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design components of the school's entrance façade, produced a magnificent artistic outcome for architecture in general, and for the school in particular, giving it a façade that rivaled other forms of art.

The Holy Qur'an encompassed the aspects of religious life, and as a result, the various arts were influenced in their use of ornamentation, with its types, forms, and creative patterns employed by the artisan-artist across the world.

Research Methodology

Research Problem

The walls of the façade of the Al-Mustansiriya School comprise design elements and components, as well as architectural complements, including the walls of the gate and the entrance of the school. These feature diverse decorations such as vegetal and geometric motifs, star patterns, and arabesque. The question arises as to the extent to which these decorative designs and their design value are reflected in the architectural façade of the building and its doors, and how they embody the philosophy of monotheism and religious beliefs as sources for ornamental designs. Their aesthetic forms represent design shapes and artistic characteristics of decorative art, known as *Arabesque*, which is strongly expressed in ornamental designs on walls. The designs are similar in nature, revolving around unity, the absence of linear perspective, and the notion of infinity. Here, lines serve to form ornamentation of various kinds, without boundaries.

The Muslim artist discovered a new world through embodying forms on the walls of the building façade, which carried doctrinal meaning and applied them as ornamental designs. These forms could be applied to stone and artistically engraved, carrying creative meanings that reflected the brilliance of planning, composition, and coordination.

Thus, the research problem lies in examining the extent of the influence of decorative design and its application on the walls of the school. What is the relationship, and what are the interrelated values, in embodying these forms on the walls from aesthetic, artistic, and functional perspectives, in accordance with Islamic doctrinal principles? This includes the types, sizes, and compositional patterns of forms, the design of lines, and the creation of ornaments as achievements of human intellect manifested in architecture. Such designs communicate with the viewer and attract the observer's gaze, being considered complementary architectural elements and decorative design components.

The research problem can be summarized in the following questions:

- What is the extent of the relationship between decorative design and the design values derived from ornamentation in its various forms on the walls of the Al-Mustansiriya School, considering them as a solid and vital element?
- To what extent can the elements and principles of design be applied to the walls of the school, as one of the architectural complements of ancient buildings in Iraq, and considering the school's walls as a source of ornamental designs Islamically, spiritually, doctrinally, and worldly?

Research Importance

The importance of the present research is manifested in the following:

1. Exploring, studying, and identifying the extent of the relationship between decorative design and design elements in order to achieve aesthetic, artistic, and functional values for the school's walls.
2. Understanding the values of decorative design in the school's walls and their spiritual and religious connections.
3. Providing an entry point for appreciation of the architectural façade through the decorative designs of doors, their coordination, and arrangement for artistic and aesthetic purposes, while

recognizing the ornamental formations on the walls as embodying both utilitarian and decorative properties.

Research Objectives

1. To reveal the impact of ornaments and their value in embodying their forms and types on the walls.
2. To uncover the philosophy of design principles and the possibility of using design elements as architectural complements applied to the walls of the Al-Mustansiriya School.

Research Hypotheses

1. The research assumes that the façade of the school includes design and ornamental values, the philosophy of monotheism, and elements and principles of design in their application.
2. The research assumes that artistic aesthetics and values are the most important outcomes that the designer may reach in the ornamental designs of the walls of the Al-Mustansiriya School, with their various forms and types.

Research Limits

The research is conducted under the following limits:

1. Temporal Limit: 625 AH / 1227 AD
2. Spatial Limit: Iraq – Baghdad

Definition of Terms

1. Design

Defined by Scott as: “a creative work that determines its purpose.”
Defined by Hammouda as: “the translation of a specific subject into a purposeful sketched idea, fully connected through execution and bearing artistic value in its aspects.”

2. Ornamentation

Defined by Ibn Manzur as: “ornament (zīna),” noting that every decoration was called ornamentation, and everything embellished or adorned was likened to it. A “decorated house” (*bayt muzakhrāf*) means a house that has been ornamented and perfected.
Defined by Johnson as: “something that is neither structural nor functional, but rather an addition to what is structural or functional. It may not be technically necessary, yet it serves the purpose of making things beautiful.”

Results

The Architectural Style in Abbasid Architecture

The Abbasid style is most clearly represented in its manifestations and distinct features, which became the foundation for Arab and Islamic ornamentation, as evident in the stucco models discovered in the architecture of the city of Samarra. These took the form of friezes covering the interior walls up to a height of about one meter, as seen in the palaces of *al-Jawsaq al-Khaqani*, *Balkunwara*, and *Bab al-Umma*. These styles progressed through several successive stages of development, which came to be known as the First Style, the Second Style, and the Third Style. This development occurred within a period of no more than a quarter of a century, due to the pressing need for economy of time required by the process of wall decoration, driven by the rapid pace of urban expansion in the city. This urgency compelled craftsmen to simplify their methods, leading to the emergence of the aforementioned styles, which differ from one another in terms of the nature of their elements, artistic features, and methods of execution in Islamic architecture.

Mesopotamia extended for a distance of 900 kilometers, from the slopes of the Armenian Plateau to the sources of the Tigris and Euphrates rivers, and down to the Arabian Gulf, which terminated at the city of Ur. Several civilizations succeeded one another in this land since the fourth millennium BC. Among the most important civilizations in this region were the Sumerian civilization in the south, the Akkadian civilization in central Iraq, and the Babylonian civilization, centered in the city of Babylon, which reached the height of its power during the reign of Hammurabi. Architecture in Mesopotamia was distinguished by several characteristics determined by the nature of the climate and the land.

There are several Islamic artistic styles, namely:

1. **Umayyad Style**

This style was established upon the Hellenistic foundation that existed in the Levant, and it also drew from the artistic traditions of other regions under Islamic rule. The unified government enabled these traditions to blend together, while at the same time remaining consistent with the teachings of the new religion, its spirit, rituals, and Arab character.

2. **Abbasid Style**

When the Fatimids took control of Egypt and the Umayyads established rule in al-Andalus, this political independence led each state to develop its own distinctive artistic characteristics, setting it apart from other artistic traditions, even though a general sense of unity remained. It is noted that Ayyubid and Mamluk art can be considered developments of Seljuk art, which had its origins in Iran.

3. **Seljuk Style**

These are Iranian styles, the first of which was the Mongol style that appeared during the rule of the Ilkhanid dynasty in the 8th century AH.

4. **Timurid Style**

This style flourished during the rule of the Timurids in the 9th century AH.

5. **Safavid Style**

This style developed during the Safavid period, from the 10th to the 12th century AH. It was later followed by the Qajar style in the 13th century AH, which displayed clear European and Indian influences. In India, an Indo-Islamic style emerged, influenced to some extent by the Iranian style, yet retaining a distinctly Indian character. In Asia Minor, the Seljuk style was succeeded by Ottoman architecture, which extended its influence into the Levant, Iraq, and North Africa.

Baghdad – The City of Peace

The old city of Baghdad, or *Dar al-Salam*, was a circular city with a diameter of 2,700 meters, of which no trace remains today. Its original plan and method of construction can only be known through the writings of early historians. It was founded by al-Mansur, who marked its boundaries with a line of ash. Pieces of cotton soaked in oil were then placed along these lines and set alight, making the layout visible at night. Al-Mansur approved it and ordered the digging of the foundations, assigning Abu Hanifa al-Nu‘man to supervise the construction and workers.

He built a double circular wall: one outer and one inner, supported by twenty-eight towers, with four gates opening to the cardinal directions one toward Mosul, another toward Basra, a third toward Khurasan, and a fourth toward al-Sham (the Levant). These gates were architectural complexes, each consisting of two doors with a corridor between them. Above the corridor was a large reception hall covered by a dome, topped with a weather vane that moved according to the direction of the wind. The inner gate opened onto a colonnaded portico, flanked on both sides by guardhouses, and each portico could accommodate one thousand soldiers.

The walls were built of mudbrick, while the vaults were constructed of fired brick with fine workmanship. At the center of the courtyard stood the Great Mosque, of which the mihrab is preserved in the Baghdad

Museum. Nearby stood the palace known as *Qasr Bab al-Dhahab*, which was surrounded by another circular wall enclosing a residential quarter. Streets radiated outward like the spokes of a wheel, fortified with massive gates. The city remained intact until the reign of Harun al-Rashid (808 CE).

Earlier, in 768 CE, al-Mansur had established the city of al-Rusafa on the eastern bank of the Tigris, designating it as the residence of his heir, al-Mahdi, and for his troops. Urban expansion continued between Dar al-Salam and al-Rusafa or Eastern Baghdad which eventually replaced Dar al-Salam after it was abandoned.

The Al-Mustansiriya School in Baghdad

While Seljuk schools, particularly those established by Nizam al-Mulk, were limited to teaching Islamic law according to the Sunni Shafi'i school, Baghdad witnessed, during the era of the Abbasid caliph al-Mustansir Billah, the construction of the Al-Mustansiriya School between 1227 and 1232 CE. The school was designed to teach all four Sunni madhhabs. It is a rectangular building consisting of a large courtyard surrounded by arcades. At the center of each side is an iwan, each measuring 6 meters in width. On both sides of each iwan, two lecture halls were provided. The student halls were two stories high and located at the ends of the iwans, supported by vaults resting on shoulders. The school's architecture reflects the characteristics of Iranian architectural constructions.

The patterns and styles of presenting Islamic ornamentation in the school may include geometric, calligraphic, structural, or natural motifs, often combined in composite forms on the walls. This diversity of styles follows the principles governing the design of the decorative structure, which represents the purpose and specific aim of Islamic architectural ornamentation, reflecting the nature of the medium, the engineering of the decoration, and its formal compositions.

Figure 1. The Patterns and Styles of Presenting Islamic Ornamentation

The Al-Mustansiriya School, established in 625 AH / 1227 CE by the Abbasid Caliph al-Mustansir Billah in the center of Baghdad, is considered one of the oldest Arab-Islamic universities. It played a significant role in teaching Islamic jurisprudence according to the four Sunni madhhabs and has produced many eminent scholars across various fields since its founding. Over time, its name changed from the Al-Mustansiriya School to Al-Mustansiriya University, which welcomed students from across the Arab world.

Abdul Latif al-Mu'adhidi (a folkloric researcher on the Al-Mustansiriya School) notes that the importance of the school lies in being the first institution dedicated to all four Islamic madhhabs, whereas previous schools specialized in only one or two madhhabs. Its goal was to unify the Muslim community to confront opposing ideological currents, making it a model that inspired the construction of many subsequent schools. Its rules and regulations served as a guiding framework for later educational institutions. The

school became a center for scholars and literati, attracting students from around the world. It had a profound impact on Islamic culture, serving as a hub for teaching the principles and branches of Islamic law, the Hadith of the Prophet (peace be upon him), mathematics, medicine, and other sciences.

In terms of planning, the Al-Mustansiriya School is a famous Abbasid building, named after its founder, Caliph al-Mustansir Billah, who established it on the eastern side of Baghdad along the Tigris River, where it still stands today. Construction began in 625 AH / 1227 CE and was completed in 631 AH / 1234 CE, with substantial funds spent on its building. The caliph personally attended its inauguration and transferred thousands of precious books, containing religious and literary sciences, to the school's library. A specialized team was appointed to organize and classify these books.

Figure 2. Al-Mustansiriya School

Principles and Ornamentation in Wall Paintings

Every science, art, and craft has rules and principles upon which ornamentation is based, as with other forms of art. These rules are often derived from nature, specifically including the following:

- **Balance:** This is a fundamental principle in Islamic ornamentation. In its comprehensive sense, balance represents an integrated artistic composition in the distribution of elements, units, and colors within the space surrounding the artwork. Examples in nature demonstrate this principle, though the most beautiful representation can be seen in trees and flowers, where shapes and colors are distributed in a harmonious and aesthetically pleasing manner.
- **Symmetry:** This is one of the most important principles underpinning ornamentation in Islamic wall art. Symmetry can take several forms, as illustrated in (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Examples of Symmetry

- **Partial Symmetry:** This includes compositions in which one part completes the other within the wall painting.

- **Complete Symmetry:** In this type, the composition is fully mirrored with identical formations arranged in opposite or contrasting directions.
- **Branching:** Most decorative compositions often include branching, which occurs in several forms:
 - **Branching from a Point:** Lines, units, and shapes extend outward from a central point.
 - **Branching from a Line:** Shapes and units branch out from straight or curved lines, either on one side or both sides. Natural examples include palm fronds, the spread of leaves, and tree branches.
- **Repetition:** Repetition takes many forms, combining multiple decorative patterns into composed shapes. It involves more than one decorative unit within the design. Repetition is clearly manifested in plants, such as wheat ears and corn stalks, and in living creatures, such as flocks of birds and caravans of camels.

Characteristics of Ornamentation in Wall Art

The decorative wall surface is distinguished by its reliance on the specific properties of the material used, whether structural or constructive (brick, adobe, stucco, or stone), as well as the preparation of the artistic decorative subject in geometric and structural forms, and the surface dimensions. These two factors govern the process of decorative design on the building's wall, shaping the material, semantic, and aesthetic composition of the ornamentation. Preparation may involve segmented pieces, flat surfaces, or carving on the surfaces of façades, walls, columns, arches, or ceilings, in accordance with their physical, chemical, and mechanical properties. Additionally, the environmental context relating to the type of space designated for the decorative surface and its natural surroundings must be considered by the designer before construction, in preparation for the components and elements of the circular Islamic decorative surface.

Key characteristics include:

- **Avoidance of Empty Space** (*Himaya al-Faragh*).
- **Decorative Flattening** (*Al-Tastih al-Zukbrufi*).
- **Avoidance of Direct Imitation of Nature.**
- **Repetition.**
- **Illustrative Drawing.**
- **Assigning a Philosophical Role to Color.**

The Muslim artist tended to fill spaces with ornamentation to eliminate emptiness, a feature that is prominent in most wall decorations of Islamic architecture. Western observers have described this phenomenon in Muslim art as a “fear of empty space.”

- **Marble** is rare in Islamic wall art; instead, the Muslim artist favored flat representations and substituted relief or three-dimensional effects with coloring and gilding to reduce the impact of sculptural forms in wall decorations.
- The Muslim artist depicted examples as imagined rather than copying natural forms, avoiding representations of living creatures, which belong solely to the creation of God.
- **Repetition** was used to overcome the problem of empty space and is applied across various Islamic arts, including architecture (e.g., pine motifs).
- The artist employed **illustrative representation**, as seen in manuscript illustrations, such as the *Al-Wasiti* illustrations for the *Maqamat al-Hariri*.
- **Color** was used in Islamic arts, including walls, to achieve aesthetic effects, with blue, green, and gold being prominent, particularly in religious architecture.

Flat Islamic geometric designs relied on geometric principles in composition, employing repetition, layering, variety, balance, rhythm, proportion, and scale, with line and movement as key elements. Geometric designs often feature **symmetry**, whether in a two-unit arrangement leading to four-unit symmetry. By shading one unit and leaving the next uncolored, two-unit symmetry can be observed. Omitting color entirely reveals four-unit symmetry (as shown in Figure 4).

Figure 4. Example of Four-Unit Symmetry

Discussion

Description and Analysis of Research Sample Models

Sample No.: (1)

- **Architectural Element:** Walls of the Al-Mustansiriya School (*al-Dunka*)
- **Type:** Walls
- **Location:** Baghdad – Al-Rusafa
- **Building Date:** 625 AH / 1227 CE

Figure 5. a, b) Walls of the Al-Mustansiriya School (Al-Dunka)

General Description

Above the gate, there are several cornices with curved forms shaping the dome, each carved with distinct ornamentation. Every cornice or band differs from the others in terms of the carved stone decorations, and Quranic verses are inscribed in one of the recognized Arabic scripts. Among the decorations on the gate wall are **star-shaped motifs (ṭabaq al-najmi)**, curved and broken lines with prominent protrusions from the original surface, giving the impression of fractured and bent crosses between the star motifs. The raised bands on the wall surface represent the first decorative level, combining geometric forms (quadrilaterals) with depth. The wall also features plant motifs, and the star-shaped designs extend infinitely, with grooves defining each section.

The composition includes large and small plant ornaments, as well as geometric patterns of the eight-pointed star, closed within themselves and extending from one star motif to another. This represents a unified decorative unit commonly found on the school walls, characterized by multiplicity and diversity surrounding the gate. Despite the variety of geometric lines in the star motifs, the Muslim artist creates a sense of divine order, reflecting religious conviction and the eternal existence of the One God, and expressing the concept of the Creator. The plant motifs are harmonized despite their diversity, evoking the image of sparkling celestial stars and conveying the idea of **tawḥīd** (oneness of God).

Islamic art, rooted in religious belief, reflects the life and consciousness of the Muslim artist, integrating both religious and worldly elements. Geometric and plant forms collectively embody the unity of the Islamic spirit underlying decorative compositions. When a viewer approaches the school and observes its façade in this manner, the spiritual atmosphere commands reverence and solemnity. The gate consists of multiple cornices and carvings arranged in layers, each with its own technique, material, and distinct Islamic artistic character. This artistic complexity captivates the observer, imparting an aesthetic and spiritual value that reflects the divine creation of nature and its inherent beauty.

Sample No.: (2)

- **Architectural Element:** Gate
- **Type:** School Gate
- **Location:** Baghdad – Al-Rusafa
- **Building Date:** 625 AH / 1227 CE

Figure 6. a) Wooden Door, b) School Gate

General Description

The school gate features numerous interlaced decorations and lines that form geometric motifs, including eight-pointed and five-pointed star patterns within a defined frame that guides the lines to form these shapes. Without the wooden frame, the lines would extend infinitely. The door is made of **Jawi wood**, with a multi-layered frame of bands divided into three sections, with the central section larger than the upper and lower sections.

The door also includes sculptural protrusions on its sides, topped with wooden blocks divided into recessed forms shaped like small domes, surmounted by a small cornice with alternating recessed and raised sections. These elements provide structural strength and aesthetic appeal, highlighting the beauty of geometric carvings, star motifs, and elevated grooves on the door surface. The design demonstrates the skill and creativity of the Muslim artist, integrating form, function, and spiritual symbolism, as the school served to teach the four Islamic legal schools.

The ornamentation on the door forms a harmonious unit in architectural style, unifying the design system. The thick carved lines are arranged as units or wooden strips, merged to create a rhythmic pattern. Despite the repetition of star motifs and interior decorations, the interplay of light and shadow on the wooden surface enhances the aesthetic impact, reflecting the natural material and divine creation.

Above the door, an arch shaped like a dome features a wooden cornice with plant motifs. The artist incorporated stems and leaves with a geometric approach, reflecting principles of symbolism and abstraction. The most exquisite Islamic plant ornamentation, **arabesque**, is represented here, with floral motifs that bend and interlace symmetrically and regularly. These raised plant forms on the door surface create a cohesive structural unit. The variation in surfaces produces contrasts of light and shadow within the dome decorations, enhancing the beauty and characteristics of arabesque art, combining geometric and plant motifs, and emphasizing the elegance of curved lines as an integrated decorative unit.

Sample No.: (3)

- **Architectural Element:** Wall Above the Gate
- **Type:** Wall
- **Location:** Baghdad – Al-Rusafa
- **Building Date:** 625 AH / 1227 CE

Figures 7. The main gate of the Al-Mustansiriya School and Mosque.

General Description

Observing the wall above the gate, which rises approximately 8 meters, it consists of multiple cornices, shapes, and carvings, both recessed and raised. These forms demonstrate the Muslim artist's intent to communicate to the viewer the intricate arrangement of interlaced geometric and plant motifs alongside star-shaped designs with recessed forms. Several bands of Quranic inscriptions are surrounded by small, interwoven plant motifs, enhancing the aesthetic appeal and elegance of the wall above the main gate of the Al-Mustansiriya School and Mosque.

The wall incorporates various shapes, including arches, triangles, and flat surfaces, each containing geometric patterns such as eight-pointed, five-pointed, and quadrilateral stars. These motifs, integrated across the surface, demonstrate the artist's mastery and creativity, remaining visually striking to this day. The artist employed both recessed and raised carving techniques, filling the remaining spaces with plant motifs such as leaves, flowers, and fruits, designed to appear naturally emerging from branches. Careful attention was given to the size and positioning of these elements, balancing symmetry and contrast.

Through this work, the Muslim artist conveys spiritual and cultural significance. The abstract arabesque motifs reflect a connection to divine and eternal forces, with repetitive geometric and decorative patterns that avoid monotony while maintaining harmony. The geometric precision evident on the wall and wooden gate highlights Islamic art as a system of similarity, symmetry, and alignment. This composition embodies religious and aesthetic principles, reflecting the Muslim architect's approach to interpreting and integrating plant, geometric, and calligraphic motifs into a unified artistic and decorative design.

Conclusion

The analysis of the wall surfaces of the Al-Mustansiriya School gate, focusing on geometric and plant designs, revealed that they adhere to a mathematical and geometric system in the philosophy of design realization.

A geometric system is evident, resulting from intersecting lines moving clockwise and counterclockwise, producing star-shaped motifs with eight, four, or five points, reflecting adherence to a unified geometric compositional system.

Geometric units and cornices were distributed across the school wall by integrating geometric, plant, and calligraphic motifs, aiming to achieve absolute aesthetic beauty and demonstrating the artist's ability to apply these designs effectively to the wall.

Most of the artistic works in the Al-Mustansiriya School achieved design value through the variation of forms and stone carvings, with repetition and symmetry contributing to visual impressiveness, aesthetic splendor, and decorative unity.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends the following:

Emphasize studying natural forms to reveal the underlying relationships in the composition and design of motifs according to their construction logic and realization in refined materials, especially geometric and plant motifs.

Conduct detailed studies on the design principles embodied in the walls of other schools.

Suggestions

The researcher proposes the following studies:

Conduct a comparative study of the walls of Al-Mustansiriya School and other schools in the Arab world, analyzing the motifs used by Muslim artists and their underlying principles and reasons.

Study the formation of geometric, plant, and calligraphic motifs and their design principles on the facades of mosques and schools featuring Islamic artistic styles.

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